

GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER

101035819

This project has received funding from the European Union's
Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme

ENLIGHT RISE- RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA WITH AND FOR SOCIETY: LEVERAGING DIGITAL
INNOVATION FOR A GREENER AND HEALTHIER EUROPE

WP No	Del. Rel. No	Del No	Title	Lead beneficiary
1	D1.6	D6	ENLIGHT R&I-SG Sustainability Report	UBx

Nature	Dissemination Level	Related to Del. No (if applicable)
Report	Public	D1.1; D1.2; D1.4

Description (short)
Report describing the strategy for ensuring the long-term sustainability of the R&I-SG and embedding this structure in the long-term ENLIGHT strategy.

Document Version Control		
Version 0.1	Originated by: Ubx	16/04/2024
Version 0.2	Originated by: UT	01/07/2024
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15585433	

The content of this deliverable represents the views of the author only and is his/her sole responsibility. The European Commission and the Agency do not accept any responsibility for use that may be made of the information it contains.

TABLE OF CONTENT

1. OVERVIEW OF PREVIOUS RELATED DELIVERABLES.....	1
1.1. BENCHMARKING REPORT OF GOOD PRACTICES IN RSOs (D1.1)	1
1.2. OPERATIONAL GUIDELINES AND SERVICE OFFER OF R&ISG (D1.2)	2
1.3. SUPPORT KIT FOR RESEARCHERS TO ASSIST THEM IN BUILDING THEIR COLLABORATIVE RESEARCH PROPOSALS (D1.4)	2
2. THE ENLIGHT R&I – SUPPORT GROUP IN RISE	2
2.1. ROLE OF THE R&I SUPPORT GROUP	2
2.2. ACTIVITIES OF THE R&I SUPPORT GROUP	3
3. ENSURING CONTINUITY OF THE R&I SG ACTIVITIES IN THE NEW ENLIGHT ERASMUS+ PROJECT	5
3.1. SUSTAINABILITY VIA ENLIGHT (2024- 2027)	5
3.2. ENLIGHT EXPERT NETWORK (EEN).....	7

University acronyms

Participant organizing name	Short name	Country
University of Bordeaux	Ubx	FR
Ghent University	Ugent	BE
Comenius University Bratislava	CU	SK
University of the Basque Country	UPV/EHU	ES
National University of Ireland, Galway NUI	Galway	IR
University of Göttingen	UGOE	DE
University of Groningen	RUG	NL
University of Tartu	UT	EE
Uppsala University	UU	SE
University of Bern	Ubern	CH

Introduction

This deliverable describes the activities of the Research and Innovation Support Group (R&I SG) within the ENLIGHT RISE H2020 project framework and outlines how they will be sustained within the ENLIGHT Erasmus+ project (2023-2027). In the submitted ENLIGHT RISE proposal, Task 1.2.3, entitled "Sustainability of the ENLIGHT R&I SG (M18-M36)," committed to achieving the following goal: « *The partners will develop a strategy for ensuring the long-term sustainability of the R&I-SG and embedding this structure in the long term ENLIGHT strategy. This includes identification of support activities that would benefit from greater coordination, and opportunities for funding these. The group will also examine how partners who are frontrunners in specific areas could support other universities in building similar capacity in those fields. In collaboration with WP9 the R&I-SG will also contribute to networking with different stakeholders and to making policy recommendations.* »

1. Overview of previous related deliverables

1.1. Benchmarking report of good practices in RSOs (D1.1)

An analysis and benchmark of best practices among ENLIGHT partner research support offices (RSOs) were conducted with a focus on identifying strengths and good practices of each partner. The analysis revealed several common trends and challenges across the surveyed universities' research support systems. The co-existence of centralized and decentralized models among RSO have been identified as well as a trend for increased specialization among support staff, expansion of consultancy and writing

services, adoption of more strategic thinking at both central and faculty levels, and a growing emphasis on engagement with European research organizations in Brussel.

1.2. Operational Guidelines and Service offer of R&ISG (D1.2)

This report aimed at formalizing the creation of the Research and Innovation Support Group (R&I SG) of the ENLIGHT alliance, presenting the services the Support Group could offer to the ENLIGHT community. It summarized the way the group operates. See section 2 for details.

1.3. Support kit for researchers to assist them in building their collaborative research proposals (D1.4)

Condensed in a concise PDF, the deliverable details the significant and practical tools of ENLIGHT and ENLIGHT RISE that empower researchers from the nine ENLIGHT universities to initiate collaborative research endeavors within the ENLIGHT alliance (the five ENLIGHT RISE Focus groups, seed money of each institution, R&I ECR mobility award and R&I Prizes, R&I observatory, repository of Good practices on research impact...).

2. The ENLIGHT R&I – Support Group in RISE

2.1. Role of the R&I Support Group

The Research and Innovation Support Group (R&I SG), comprising research support officers from the ten¹ ENLIGHT partners, served as a virtual working group established within RISE to provide support for the ENLIGHT community in European and international research and innovation proposals/projects. Staff members from each partner have been designated to participate in the R&I SG, which consists of individuals with diverse profiles such as funding officers, research funding advisers, and grant consultants. Coordinated by support staff members from the Universities of Tartu, Groningen, and Bordeaux, the R&I SG convened on a monthly basis.

The R&I SG's main goal was to support the ENLIGHT community in developing joint competitive European and international research and innovation project proposals. Its specific objectives were the following:

- Providing the ENLIGHT community with an easier and broader access to European/international funding opportunities

¹ ENLIGHT has expanded to formally include the University of Bern with the start of ENLIGHT 2.0 in November 2023.

- Identifying synergies that can be achieved in different sources of international & EC funding
- Facilitating and incentivizing research collaborations between ENLIGHT partners
- Identifying suitable funding support in response to the research ideas
- Supporting the preparation of joint research and innovation proposals

2.2. Activities of the R&I Support Group

The R&I – SG provided the following services

1. Monitoring & information service to the five pilot Focus Groups: The R&I SG examined existing and forthcoming EU and other R&I funding opportunities to support the development of collaborative research project proposals based on the topics/interests identified by researchers in each of the five Focus Groups opened during RISE.
2. Facilitating partner searches for joint R&I proposals: the R&I SG members acted as facilitators to help researchers find partners in other ENLIGHT universities through a system of partner searches hosted on the [ENLIGHT website](#) and thanks to dissemination of information by email to all main liaisons.
3. Developing and disseminating support kits and guides (D1.4).
4. Organizing the ENLIGHT RISE matchmaking event on April 29th & 30th.

The R&I – SG organized 3 sessions of best practices exchanges whereby frontrunners in a given research support topic presented their actions, followed by an open group discussion. The following sessions have been organized:

Online workshop on RSO best practices – April 22nd, 2022

1) Session 1 - incentive practices

The session began with UGOE presenting their start-up funding programmes. Ubx followed with an overview of the "*Dispositif soutien Europe*," which includes the MRSEI and Tremplin programs designed to enhance success rates during the pre-award phase. RUG then detailed incentive practices at both central and faculty levels, such as bonuses, travel grants, and support grants. Lastly, UPV/EHU discussed their incentive system for (EU) project proposals, featuring open calls for mobility, consultancy services, and justified return of indirect costs and own personnel costs.

2) Session 2 - ERC practices

The workshop continued focusing on practices that universities are implementing to increase/incentivize researcher applications to ERC schemes. UGOE highlighted their services for the ERC application phase, including candidate recruitment, budget focus, interview training, and networking opportunities. RUG presented their approach "from targeted support to talent

development," emphasizing the Netherlands Talent Scheme for ERC researchers, mock interviews, and assistance with personal strategies such as CV development and training. UT concluded the session with their expertise in proposal development, offering writing training sessions and bootcamps to support ECRs in their research endeavors.

Onsite (Bordeaux) workshop on RSO best practices – October 5th, 2022

1) Session 1 – Consultancy and writing services

During this workshop, WP1 partners presented the consultancy and writing services offered by their universities, focusing on both pre-award and post-award phases. The session began with the CU discussing what Early Career Researchers (ECRs) and the university can expect from each other in terms of efforts. GAL detailed their Research Support consultancy services, which include proposal review, graphic design, interview preparation, grant writing, training, application management, and implementation management. UPV/EHU described its support structure, differentiating between "on-demand consultancy" to promote participation in international research projects and "ad-hoc consultancy" to identify candidates for strategic university areas. Ubx showcased its comprehensive support services for researchers, including writing services and forthcoming initiatives such as workshops based on funding programs and proposal sections (methodology, impact), streamlined writing for transversal sections like gender considerations and open access, and annotated templates for successful proposals. Finally, UT presented its Grant Writing Unit (GWU), which offers extensive support ranging from idea development to application formatting and design elements.

2) Session 2 - Digital tools

RUG introduced its Research Support portal, an internally developed central hub designed to overcome the challenge of "information silos" by connecting multiple faculty intranets. UT showcased its grant matching tool for ERC applications. UU presented its Digital Research Handbook, a comprehensive guide for writing research grant proposals and managing funded projects. GAL highlighted its research community portal and tools to navigate the calls, which allow users to search for calls by funder, deadlines, career stage, and access a resource section providing practical information on the calls.

Online workshop on RSO best practices – November 9th, 2023

1) Session 1 – management/organisation of research support

RUG, UGent, and UU shared insights into their research support operations. UGent outlined the structure and management of their research support teams. UU discussed their research support organization, detailing the specific roles and functions within their team. Meanwhile, the RUG explored their centralized and decentralized funding support, emphasizing the role of Faculty Funding Officers in supporting research initiatives across their institution.

2) Session 2 – lobby in Brussels

Then participants focused on the theme of influence and lobby in Brussels. UGent shared their expertise with a presentation on "How to do lobby in Brussels". They provided insights into effective lobbying strategies within the European Union context. Additionally, RUG presented their approach to EU lobbying, offering perspectives and practices related to influencing policy and decision-making at the European level.

3) Session 3 - Mapping of EU R&I partnerships landscape

UT presented how they designed a strategy and dedicated support for UT research community to join relevant partnerships from Horizon Europe, notably the institutionalized partnerships.

3. Ensuring Continuity of the R&I SG Activities in the New ENLIGHT Erasmus+ Project

The cohesion, work habits, and approaches developed by the R&I SG during RISE have left a strong impact on how our R&I support teams are connected and work together. Ensuring the continuity of the R&I SG to support the research component of the alliance has been acknowledged as essential. Therefore, the R&I SG's activities and goals established in ENLIGHT RISE (H2020) will be continued and spread across the ENLIGHT (ERASMUS+ 2023-2027) project within WP1 "Management and governance", WP3 "Empowering academics: Knowledge Creation" and WP4 "Empowering staff: Professional development". Alongside, ENLIGHT Expert Networks (EEN) created in RISE will keep existing either formally or informally and be connected to the project to provide support, as explained in the dedicated section.

3.1. Sustainability via ENLIGHT (2024- 2027)

3.1.1. Network of influence experts – EU Strategic Watch Taskforce

The R&I Support Group had previously discussed the importance of strategic monitoring of EU policies during a workshop dedicated to EU lobbying. These activities will be addressed in WP1 of the ENLIGHT Erasmus 2024-2027. For this purpose, an EU Strategic Watch Taskforce, consisting of at least one (intelligence) expert from each partner, was established on April 10, 2024.

The scope of this activity has been defined in the proposal as developing a common "European and global partnership portfolio, linked to ENLIGHT flagships, ecosystems (cities, regions – e.g., Regional Academy), sustainable development, and digital skills, for disseminating and exploiting knowledge, sharing good practices," and enhancing ENLIGHT's regional, European, and worldwide visibility to benefit ENLIGHT's target groups (students, learners, academics, researchers, and support staff). Its aim is "to better respond to wider EU developments, dispatch EU intelligence within the ENLIGHT

community, and seek connections with the wider EU agenda and EU instruments (such as digital innovation, the Green Deal, and the New European Bauhaus)."

3.1.2. The Europe Support Network (ESN)

The R&I Support Group's mission to connect the (European) Research Support offices of the partner universities is continued through the Europe Support Network (ESN) established in WP3 "Empowering Academics: Knowledge Creation" of the ENLIGHT Erasmus 2024-2027 project. This WP aims at empowering our academics to establish knowledge creation teams integrating "challenge-based education and R&I with societal impact in the key focus areas of the alliance". The specific objective of the ESN, outlined in task 3.3, is to strengthen the alliance know-how and capacity to support its joint R&I actions with a special focus on early career researchers, capitalizing on the networks and tools developed in RISE. The ESN is defined in the proposal, the "Europe Support Network is at its core a Network of Senior R&I Support Representatives from the 10 partner Universities, connecting, guiding and leveraging the growth of collective and institutional R&I support for increased R&I collaboration excellence now and into the future." Therefore, it will pursue a similar scope of activities as the R&I SG sustaining the exchange of good practices among RSO and catering for R&I support needs and providing services to researchers, particularly early-career researchers (ECR) and those involved in European Thematic Networks (ETN).

The ESN will pursue activities aimed at enhancing joint R&I capacity, expanding and exchanging know-how, and raising the quality of institutional R&I services. A new framework called "knowledge exchange sessions" will be established twice a year to discuss topics such as funding opportunities for young researchers, grant writing, legal issues in multi-partner projects, ethics, impact, dual use, and Open Science practices (including open access and FAIR data). This network will serve as a comprehensive resource for researchers, especially early career researchers, fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange.

In addition, the ESN's scope includes supporting the application to ENLIGHT calls, especially the ENLIGHT Thematic Network (ETN – T5.1). Finally, the ESN will rely on the key tools and resources from RISE that support collaboration, such as the R&I Observatory and the Impact Repository.

3.1.3. Supporting the development of research support staff

The creation of professional networks among ENLIGHT staff will continue in the ENLIGHT Erasmus 2024-2027 project. Sustaining an active and skilled network of research support staff will be achieved by enhancing connections between universities and offering opportunities to improve skills through peer learning events known as "staff weeks." These events involve blended training opportunities organized by each participating university as part of Task 4.3. The goal of Task 4.3, titled "*administrative staff development*" is to enhance professional skills and international peer learning for

diverse array of administrative profiles and encouraging support staff to exchange ideas and experiences related to partnerships between universities and external entities. These staff weeks target employees working with external collaborations involved for instance in communication, IT Support, academic affairs (quality assurance, admissions, lifelong learning, systems and analysis), Project Support (collaboration officers), Research & Development Support, Management Support).

The joint ENLIGHT staff week program will be managed by a newly established Staff Week Taskforce, which includes staff week organizers from each of our institutions, working within their respective international offices and HR departments. The program will cover various aspects of university administration (management, including facility management, open science, alumni relations, well-being, and counseling services). Each university will host an annual staff week, with at least two participants from each member university attending. These staff weeks will be embedded into local training offer to add an international dimension to current career paths.

3.2. ENLIGHT Expert Network (EEN)

The ENLIGHT Erasmus 2024-2027 project governance strongly supports the continuation of RISE networks. A working group in the ENLIGHT Erasmus+ project has been established to develop the necessary framework for the RISE EENs within ENLIGHT (2023-2027). Terms of Reference have been agreed upon to define the conditions to propose an EEN, the status, composition, activities and operational guidelines leading to the following definition of an EEN.

3.2.1. Status of the EEN

The ENLIGHT expert networks are groups of thematic experts from at least 5 different ENLIGHT universities formed to promote knowledge sharing across the alliance. The EEN are led by at least one Chair (with the possibility for co-chairs). The aim of the EEN is to gain expertise, as well as to provide access to an exchange of experiences from other ENLIGHT experts working in the same research support field. These networks are to function with a high degree of autonomy and no ENLIGHT funding will be allocated to them, but still linked to the project to ensure their viability. Participation in the EEN is on a purely voluntary basis. In adopting and structuring the EEN, the aim is to facilitate the maintenance and growth of an R&I resource network to share knowledge and raise collective expertise.

Each EEN will be officially recognized by the Director's Board in ENLIGHT 2.0 once they have been validated, following their formal application through an EEN form and the designation of their chairperson(s).

3.2.2. Activities of the EEN

EENs will organize or participate in meetings as follows as part of their activities:

- EENs are required to have a minimum of 3 exchange sessions per year. The participation of EEN to the project general meeting is encouraged, and the alliance may facilitate possible on-site meeting for them. These General Meetings will offer space for presentations by the EEN on the agenda and programme, though it remains up to the initiative of the EEN to decide whether they would like to attend.
- EENs will be available to attend at least 1 consortium meeting (this can refer to a WP meeting, a Director's Board meeting, or any other meeting linked to the activities of the ENLIGHT alliance) per year to present the expert network's annual report and discuss current ongoing ENLIGHT initiatives thematically linked to the expert network.
- EENs will maintain the required meeting records (including agendas, attendance and minutes) on the ENLIGHT consortium SharePoint.

The following outputs are expected from all EENs:

- providing an annual report of activities in which they outline the next steps for their EEN continuing into the upcoming year as well as indicate who will be leading the network in the next working period.
- contributing expertise to ENLIGHT project activities.
- Expert networks may be consulted for advice regarding their thematic expertise/experience by any ENLIGHT Consortium project's WPs, Task leads and/or the DM directly.

To ensure continuity, RISE WP1 R&I-SG will apply to become the "EEN - *European Research Funding Network (Research and Innovation Support Group)*". This EEN will be co-chaired by Ubx, RUG and CU. While the exchange of best practices among colleagues from different ENLIGHT institutions will be sustained through the Europe Support Network (ESN), the system of partner and funding search set in RISE will be sustained through this network of support experts. This network of professionals dedicated to research support will then not only persist but also expand, seeking to integrate more support staff from the alliance to keep on its mission to foster a deeper ENLIGHT collaboration. This approach will ensure that the valuable work and connections initiated by the R&I SG will be carried forward.